

USING CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT TOOLS TO RAISE EFFICIENCY OF THE INTERNAL AUDIT FUNCTION

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Abstract:

The research aims to establish the proper application of continuous improvement in the efficiency of the internal audit function by identifying the aspects or areas affecting the efficiency of that job. The research problem was (what are the most important aspects or areas affecting the internal audit function that require continuous improvement in order to raise and improve the efficiency of that job in the government service sector). The research community was represented by internal auditing devices in the government service sector, the research sample included the internal audit device in the Municipality of Baghdad.) An interview, where the answers were taken and arranged in a table and considered (frequencies), and the cumulative frequency was found from the sum of the repetitions after they were arranged in descending order, and the cumulative ratios were found from the cumulative frequency division by the total number of iterations using the program (Microsoft Excel 2016) and using Pareto analysis As well as using a cause and effect diagram. The researchers found that there are influential aspects in the efficiency of the internal audit function, which are (experience, practical qualification, cooperation and coordination, the efficiency of completing the audit work, technology). The researchers recommended the necessity of selecting the heads and subordinates working in the internal audit body well and making it according to appropriate conditions, and the need to create an administrative unit or a section within the formations of the internal audit body of the Municipality of Baghdad specialized in maintaining the level of efficiency of the internal audit function and working to improve it.

Keywords: Improvement Tools, Efficiency, Internal Audit

Introduction

In light of the challenges faced by economic units in the intense competition environment, technological developments and scarcity of resources, which cast a shadow on the internal audit function, which led to increased pressure on the services provided by those functions. The (IIA) set a reference framework to enhance and improve the efficiency of the internal audit function, as it included a set of principles, ethics and performance standards that regulate the work of internal auditors, and it was also required under this framework the necessity of continuous improvement and development in the internal audit function to ensure the efficiency of that function. The use of continuous improvement tools (interview, analysis, etc.) Pareto, Cause and Effect Diagram) effectively contributes to reaching the appropriate arrangement that must be followed in order to begin improving the efficiency of any function within the unit.

To an increase in the efficiency of the internal audit function, as it focuses on making changes with simple payments that make it more acceptable and less resistant to change. In addition,

there are some important aspects of continuous improvement in internal auditing , which can be clarified as follows (experience, academic qualification, cooperation and coordination, completion of audit work , technology), as well as They are considered basic areas or factors affecting the efficiency of that job, but at different levels. Based on the foregoing, the research included five axes It starts with the first axis, which includes the research methodology and previous studies, the second axis is tools for continuous improvement, and the third axis is the concept of internal audit efficiency and the aspects affecting the efficiency of the internal auditor, the fourth axis is the practical aspect, to conclude the research with the fifth axis, as it includes conclusions and recommendations.

The first axis: Research Methodology and Previous Studies

First: the research methodology

1. Research problem

The problem with research is (what is most important sides or fields the mission influential job audit inner which require optimization continuous From Yes upload efficiency that job in sector government service).

2. Search objective

The research aims to:

- Establishing the proper application of continuous improvement in the efficiency of the internal audit function by identifying the aspects or areas affecting the efficiency of that job.
- Arrange the appropriate order according to level or the size of the effect each area in the efficiency of the internal audit function to initiate the process of improvement.

3. Research importance

The importance of the research stems from:

- The importance of internal audit in the organizational structure of the unit, as it is the first responsible for evaluating and evaluating the work of the unit.
- The importance of the efficiency of the internal audit function and its impact on the rest of the functions of the unit's departments.
- The importance of using continuous improvement tools in determining the areas affecting the efficiency of the internal audit function.

4. Research Hypothesis

The research is based on the following main hypothesis (there are important aspects that affect the efficiency of the internal audit function that require continuous improvement, such as experience, qualification, cooperation, completion of the audit work , and technology, respectively)

5. Community and sample research

The research community is represented by the internal auditing bodies operating in the government service sector, while the research sample included a number of individuals working in the Internal Audit and Control Authority of the Municipality of Baghdad.

Second: previous studies

The second section of the first axis includes a review of some previous foreign studies that are related to the subject of the current study.

1. Study (Ali , 2015)	
Study Title	Applying the continuous improvement method (Kaizen) in improving the audit process. (Search and he part From requirements Nile certificate accountant legal advance to the council Institute higher for studies accounting Finance / University Baghdad).
Purpose of the study	Statement of the effect of using the continuous improvement method in reducing the time of the audit process by reducing waste and increasing the quality of the audit.
the study Problem	The lack of a comprehensive review of the activities of the audit process and verification of their achievement of the objectives for which they were designed and the failure to improve them on a continuous basis leads to waste of control energy and a decrease in audit quality.
The study sample	A sample of the supervisory body in the Federal Financial Supervision Bureau.
The tool used	Checklist, Pareto analysis.
Conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ That deal with the problems that result From puppy Activities proces audit on me that it chances to improve and development As style to develop Ideas and exchange practices the good and discuss Proposals staff grow capacity The Worker and motivates him on me Do More From Yes to support Activities innovation. ▪ Non Engage members Commission censorship in state plan audit Than reflected negatively on me to implement plan, no Complete Determine the time chart to report in Stage planning but Complete planning on me level Circle submissive to check Than Makes proces comparison the time Actual by chart in Form tracking Phase Issuance the report proces Formalism As a result, no Determine Reasons deviation picture min. ▪ Weakness Approval Arbitrage the time in Determine the time and energy planned to check all paragraph from vertebrae a program audit Than Lead to me weakness censorship on me the time for operation audit and late Achievement Reports and therefore get waste in and time and effort.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Necessity interest Management Diwan conducting adjustment gradual in proces audit From during Identify on me Hurdles to implement the plan and collect suggestions to improve mediated by difference optimization continuous from workers. ▪ Didn't you review? Continuous for procedures and decisions administrative own with activities proces audit and note Results that it was completed Access to her From during Issuance this is procedures and decisions and from then attempt straightened and modify them picture continuous. ▪ Approval methods statistic Such as existing examination And the Scheme Pareto in Determine More Defects effect in Reports Finance and therefore state procedures that reduce or prevent repetition.

2. Study (Mohammed , 2019)

Study Title	Factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal audit function. (Published research, Scientific Journal of Economics and Trade, Ain Shams University, Egypt, for the year 2019).
Purpose of the study	This study aims to test the factors that affect the effectiveness of internal auditing from the perspective of employees in the internal audit function.
the study Problem	What are the factors affecting the effectiveness of internal audit?
The study sample	Internal auditors working in Egyptian government units in Menoufia Governorate, Arab Republic of Egypt.
The tool used	Resolution.
Conclusions	The study concluded that the professional competence, independence and objectivity of the internal auditor, the quality of performance, the support of senior management, coordination and cooperation between the internal and external auditors affect the effectiveness of the internal audit.
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The necessity of establishing an institute of internal auditors in Egypt to take care of the profession of internal auditing. ▪ The necessity of activating the internal audit function in the governmental unit through the availability of appropriate resources for it. ▪ The need to raise the efficiency of the internal auditors by providing education and development.

3. study(gain , 2020)

Study Title	Determinants of the effectiveness of internal audit departments in government units in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. (Published research, Alexandria Journal of Accounting Research, Faculty of Commerce, Egypt, Volume 4, and Issue 2 for the year 2020).
Purpose of the study	Define parameters effectiveness departments Review interior in units governmental Kingdom Arabic Saudi Arabia by defining the sub-determinants.
the study Problem	Determine factors or determinants that achieve efficacy in departments Review interior in units governmental Kingdom Arabic Saudi Arabia Which should be taken care of by the competent officials in this regard.
The study sample	Government agencies and public institutions in the Kingdom Arabic Saudi Arabia.
The tool used	The resolution.
Conclusions	Determined both professional competence and the external auditor's dependence on the work of the internal auditor
Recommendations	Providing the necessary factors that would enhance the professional competence of the auditor and increase the degree of dependence of the external auditor on the work of the internal auditor.

4. study(Gerissa , 2022)

Study Title	Factors influential in upload efficiency and efficacy loneliness censorship interior and its role in to improve performance a job municipalities. (Published research, Arab Journal for Scientific Publishing, College of Commerce, Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and Issue 43 for the year 2022).
Purpose of the study	Identify the factors affecting raising the efficiency and effectiveness of the internal control unit and its role in improving the performance of the work of municipalities.
the study Problem	What are the factors affecting raising the efficiency and effectiveness of the internal control unit and its role in improving the performance of the work of the Fuheis Municipality
The study sample	Fuheis Municipality.
The tool used	An analytical study.
Conclusions	The function of the internal control unit is an integral part of the government financial management and an essential element in the financial management system in the government sector. The most important influencing factors are efficiency and objectivity.
Recommendations	The need to carry out a continuous examination of the efficiency and effectiveness of the internal control unit.

In this research, we will focus on some important aspects of continuous improvement in the internal audit function that affect the efficiency of that job.

The Second Axis: Tools for Continuous Improvement

Continuous improvement in the implementation of improvement processes is based on the use of many tools and techniques, which are used in both quality management and continuous improvement of processes and functions, and most of these tools are used to diagnose the aspects and influencing factors and solve problems, as Accuracy depends in collecting and analysing data and information. The most important tools for improvement are personal interviews, analysis Pareto, the cause and effect method, and the following is an illustration of these tools:

1. Method of Personal Interviews

It is to take the opinion of workers and employees and the suggestions presented by them as a contribution to the production process, considering them closest to the process and having full knowledge of it. This technique is used to identify factors, areas or problems, whether internal or external, and to collect information (Abu Al-Nasr, 2015: 151), It is also known as one of the tools Which is used to collect and record process data in an organized manner, as data collection and analysis leads to help identifying problems within the process and making improvements (Murad, 2017: 77).

2. Pareto Analysis

Pareto analysis is one of the improvement tools in most aspects of life, and it is an effective tool aimed at ensuring the efficiency of any job within the economic unit, as it follows a consistent approach in analysing problems and addressing their causes to bring about improvements in the service or job to be improved. (Heizer & et. al., 2020:252).

It was defined as a graphic method for classifying problems or causes according to their level of importance, and it is often referred to as the 80/20 rule. The purpose of Pareto's analysis is to distinguish between the few vital and the many abiotic. It is also characterized as a direct technique that includes arranging the elements of information about the types of the problem or the causes of the problem in order of importance, and it is usually measured by "frequency of occurrence". They can be used to highlight areas in which useful decisions will be made , and Pareto's analysis is based on the phenomenon of relatively few causes causing the majority of effects (2010: 561-562). et.al, & Slack).

Pareto analysis can be done by making a list of causes or possible aspects that affect the efficiency of any job with the need to specify the time period, and then arrange those aspects from most important to least important and according to repetitions, and then draw the chart using the program (Microsoft Excel 2016).

3. Cause - Effect Diagrams

Also called Ishikawa diagram or fishbone diagram, it is a schematic technique used to discover potential locations of problems that hinder reaching the appropriate level of efficiency in any function within the unit (227). 2017: et.al, & Heizer)... And a cause and effect diagram can be drawn through three steps, the first is to identify the main problem or the goal of improvement and then identify the main components of the problem or the goal and consider them as secondary problems and then start searching for causes (Khunji, 2016:4-5). The researchers see the possibility of using continuous improvement tools to determine the areas affecting the efficiency of the internal audit function.

Third Axis: The Concept of Internal Audit Efficiency and the Aspects Affecting the Efficiency of the Internal Auditor.

The concept of efficiency is known as the best way to use resources, as well as the ability to minimize the use of resources without compromising the goals set (Al-Jraisat, 2022:392) The competence of the internal auditor was also defined as the ability of the internal auditor to apply the necessary knowledge and skill when performing internal audit tasks (Lakhdar, 2016: 104). Knowledge and skills and competencies other Factors a task and necessary effect on me auditor efficiency interns when they perform for jobs audit internal. And help them in evaluation conditions the work current and issues emerging and presenting advice and recommendations to improve Activities organizational, as Proof efficiency checker inner from during get on me Certificates and qualifications professional the occasion (Trang & Doan, 2022:4).

The efficiency of the internal audit function requires the availability of experience, qualification and appropriate knowledge in the field of internal auditing, as well as the need to maintain it through keeping pace with and understanding developments in the audit function and the work of the unit and the availability of technological tools and methods, as well as other matters no less important than those mentioned (Lubna and Hajira, 2019). 22). as for the influencing aspects, they include the following:

1. Experience

achieve availability Experience and skills necessary in auditors entrants Efficiency and behavior the good in their work And therefore necessity that available Of experience Occasion in Sections audit internal, then Acquire checker Experience From continuity of practice the work proofreader for periods time ongoing or From During receive it training appropriate (Putri&Nengzih, 2021:134)).

2. Academic Qualification Of The Auditor

The possession of the individuals working in internal auditing with the appropriate academic qualification helps them to exercise more professional care while performing the tasks and thus achieve the desired results efficiently. (IIA) also stressed the necessity of having the appropriate academic and professional qualifications and certificates to perform the internal audit function efficiently (IIA, 2020: 37).

3. Cooperation And Coordination

The cooperation and coordination between the individuals working in the internal audit departments, the administration and the rest of the unit members is very important in improving the efficiency of the internal audit function. Conditions for this not affecting the independence, impartiality and objectivity of the internal auditor (70. IIA, 2020).

4. Performing the Audit Work

The need for the unit management and the internal audit department to work continuously in order to provide the appropriate material and human resources and the necessary plans to complete the audit work efficiently. In addition, the department should put in place the necessary procedures that would encourage the auditor to take into account the exercise of professional care in his work, such as granting material and moral rewards As well as setting timings to complete tasks and holding periodic meetings and other things) Anne pitt, 2014:34-35) .

5. Technology

The adoption of technological methods, tools and ready-made programs in the field of internal auditing and the appropriate experience in their use contribute to improving the efficiency of the internal audit function. (2018:12 Sulanjana & Puspitasari)

The researchers believe that it is possible to use continuous improvement tools (personal interview, analysis). Pareto, cause and effect diagram) to identify some of the basic areas that affect the efficiency of the internal audit function and analyse them in a practical and scientific manner in order to achieve the main goal of continuous improvement, which is the efficiency of the internal audit function

Fourth Axis: the Practical Aspect

The following figure, Figure (1), shows how to use improvement tools to improve the efficiency of the internal audit function.

Shape (1): Continuous improvement tools to improve the efficiency of internal auditing

(Source: Prepared by the researchers)

1. Personal Interviews

Table (1) shows the results of the personal interviews conducted by the researchers, analysing the answers to the repetitions and arriving at the cumulative frequency and cumulative percentages, which will be adopted as inputs to the Pareto analysis chart in Figure (2).

Table (1): Analyse personal interview answers

Cumulative percentage	cumulative frequency	Repetition	the reasons	secondary hypotheses
30%	9	8	Experience	a
53%	16	7	Qualification	B
73%	22	6	Coordination and cooperation	T
90%	27	5	Performing the audit work	w
100%	30	3	technology	c
		29	the total	
		29	All factors are influencing	main premise
All the individuals who were interviewed confirmed that the continuous improvement in all aspects of internal auditing has an impact on raising and improving the efficiency of internal auditing, and this is evidence of the proof .of the main hypothesis				

(Source: Prepared by the researchers)

previous table (1) shows the frequency of the answers of the sample members (29 employees) who were interviewed and the collection of their answers about the influential aspects In the

efficiency of the internal audit function and arranged in descending order, then reaching the frequency total, and then finding the frequency ratio, which will be adopted as inputs to the analysis (Pareto chart).

2. Pareto Analysis

Figure (2) shows the Pareto chart, which will prompt the entry of the results reached by personal interviews to conduct the appropriate analyses.

Shape (2): Pareto analysis chart for interview results

(Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the results of Excel 2016)

Figure (2) above, the Pareto analysis chart, shows that the size of the impact of experience on the efficiency of the internal audit function reached an impact rate of more than (20%), followed by the academic qualification, then cooperation and coordination, then the completion of the audit work, and finally technology.

3. Cause and Effect Diagram

Figure (3) shows the important aspects of continuous improvement in the internal audit function that must be improved in order to achieve the main objective of continuous improvement, which is the efficiency of the internal audit function.

Figure (3): Cause and Effect Diagram

(Source: Prepared by the researchers)

The previous figure shows that the main objective of using continuous improvement tools is to improve the efficiency of the internal audit function. sides or fields the mission influential job audit inner in sector government service which require optimization Continuous to (aspects related to staff, including experience and qualification, aspects related to the role of management, including cooperation and achievement, and aspects related to appropriate support represented by technology).

And thus the acceptance of the main hypothesis (there are important aspects that affect the efficiency of the internal audit function that require continuous improvement, which are expertise, qualification, cooperation, achievement, technology, respectively).

Fifth Axis: Conclusions and Recommendations

First: The Conclusions

- 1) Both (personal interviews, Pareto analysis, cause and effect diagram) are the most effective continuous improvement tools in improving the efficiency of jobs in the government service unit in general and the internal audit function in particular.
- 2) Personal interviews, it was found that there are aspects, areas, or factors that affect the efficiency of the internal audit function in government service units.
- 3) The main areas affecting the efficiency of the internal audit function have been identified, in general, in three areas (staff, role, etc.). management, appropriate support).
- 4) The fields are also divided the basic The three influential By five sub-areas (experience and qualification pertain to employees, cooperation and achievement pertain to management support, technology pertain to appropriate support).

Second: Recommendations

1. It is necessary to create an administrative unit or a section within the formations of the internal audit apparatus of the Municipality of Baghdad, specialized in maintaining the level of efficiency of the internal audit function and working to improve it.
2. Increasing interest in areas of improving the efficiency of the internal auditor by setting up the responsible departments for a mechanism or program for improvement that includes each of the areas or factors that are most important and affect the efficiency of internal auditing .
3. Necessity Hassan Selection the bosses and subordinates staff in device audit internal through:
 - ❖ Attracting experts and specialists in the field of internal auditing and taking into account the continuity of the audit work for a period of no less than (5) years.
 - ❖ As a proactive measure , legal provisions and paragraphs may be set that require the appointment of internal auditors with the appropriate academic qualifications.
4. Can to treat fields or factors influential in efficiency Function audit inner From during :
 - ❖ Establish and configure effective communication channels between the administration and the internal auditor, for example , an integrated system for sending reports, and that the auditors work as a team to achieve harmony as well as coordinate work with other departments.
 - ❖ need for the administration to set timelines for the completion of tasks, activating an appropriate mechanism for granting Financial and moral rewards to motivate employees to relieve work pressure.
 - ❖ Availability of tools, technological methods and ready-made and appropriate electronic programs in the field of internal audit and work to enhance expertise in its field.

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